

Modeling De-extinction: A Computational Approach to Back-breeding Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we look at an interesting biologically inspired computational problem. De-extinction, or bringing back extinct species, has been an important problem for conservationists. One of the key mechanisms suggested for this is back-breeding- selectively breeding closely related species in an attempt to get back the original species. In this paper, we consider a simplified toy model, considering only two individuals in each generation and modeling the formation of a new generation as a random combination of the chromosomes from both the individuals in the previous generation. We also added mutations, which are the driving force of the de-extinction process, and used computer simulations to predict the approximate number of generations required to bring back the original species with respect to the probability of mutation for any given generation. Our results were interesting, we observed that as the mutation probability ranged from 1% to 100%, the expected number of generations was roughly constant, while from 0.01% to 1%, the average number of generations steeply decreased before stabilizing.

Keywords: *de-extinction, back breeding, mutation, gene pool, genetic reconstruction*

1. Introduction

The use of mathematical and computational models in genetics has led to a paradigm shift in the field of biology [Bur11]. In population genetics, the work of R.A. Fisher, S. Wright, and J. B.S. Haldane has been influential [Tho90], leading to several key insights, such as that Mendelian inheritance preserves genetic variation on which natural selection acts. There is also some prior literature on using mathematical tools to study the breeding of organisms with certain genotypes and the short-term and long-term effects of the same. For instance,

mathematical modeling and software tools for breeding value estimation based on phenotypic, pedigree and genomic information for cows have been proposed [BJP⁺22]. In this paper, we use such tools to look at a more specific problem: that of de-extinction, or bringing back the genotype of an extinct animal through breeding animals with similar genotypes with the intention of getting the target genotype after multiple generations of inbreeding [RSG16], in a method known as back breeding [Sha17]. De-extinction has been an important problem for conservationists [Nov18] and has applications to preserving ecosystems, and maintaining keystone species, and biodiversity. We studied a toy model of the situation where we consider only two organisms in each generation and a gene pool G consisting of the chromosomes of the two organisms in the initial generation, which is then distributed amongst the two organisms in each generation. We then ran computer simulations to estimate how long it takes for the exact genotype of any one of the two organisms in the initial generation to reappear.

2. Methodology

2.1. Aim of the Study

The study explores the relationship between the probability of mutation and the expected number of generations needed for a target genotype to appear in the gene pool. Additionally, the statistical distribution of the expected value of the number of generations as the probability of mutation ranges over the natural numbers from 1 to 100 is observed.

2.2. Research Design

The research is experimental in nature, with in-silico experiments being used to study the expected number of generations for a genotype to recur. Following that, both qualitative and quantitative observations have been made about the collected data.

2.2.2. Model

The simplified model of the problem we consider is as follows: We have a master gene pool consisting of all the genes the organism can have. In this simplification, we consider a master pool 1, 2, ..., 10. We represent the two organisms in the initial generation by the arrays A_1 and A'_1 with m elements each where m is the number of chromosomes, and each gene is selected

from the master pool. We allow the same gene to be repeated multiple times in the genotype. The two organisms in the n th generation are represented by the arrays A_n and A'_n . In each generation, represented by an iteration in the code, the gene pool (consisting of all the individual genes in A_n and A'_n) is redistributed amongst the organisms in the next generation A_{n+1} and A'_{n+1} . We additionally model mutations, which are the 'driving force' of the process of genetic diversity. We assign a probability of mutation p such that in each recursive step, there's a $p\%$ chance that one of the genes in the genotype of either of the two organisms is replaced by another one from the master gene pool.

For instance, if A_1 is [1, 2, 3, 4] and A'_1 is [6, 5, 4, 3], A_2 might be [1, 4, 3, 4] and A'_2 might be [2, 5, 3, 6]. If the probability of mutation is 10%, there's a 10% chance that any one of the genes would be replaced by another one from the pool 1, 2, ..., 10, and we might now have $A_2 = [1, 4, 3, 4]$ and $A'_2 = [9, 5, 3, 6]$, where the gene on the 1st locant of the 2nd organism was replaced by the 9th gene from the gene pool.

2.2.3. Variables

The independent variables in the study are the number of chromosomes and the probability of mutation. The dependent variable is the number of generations. To conduct the study, we looked at cases where the values of m were 3, 4, 5 and 6 respectively. We ran simulations to study the amount of generations that occur before any of the original genotypes is repeated again. Formally, we ran experiments to find the expected value of n such that $A_n = A_1$ or $A'_n = A_1$ or $A_n = A'_1$ or $A'_n = A'_1$. We studied how the expected value of the number of generations varies with the probability of mutation.

2.3. Data Collection Procedure

The simulations were run using code written in Python. Python is a widely used programming language for web development, data science, and general-purpose programming. Its characteristics, such as its expressive and straightforward syntax that makes code reading and writing simple, make it appropriate for running simulations. In our code, we used the NumPy library to store the values in the genotype as an array and model the simulation process with ease.

To conduct the simulations, code for particular values of m and p was executed. For each

set of values, we ran 500 simulations before taking the average.

3. Results

We ran simulations for $m = 3, 4,$ and 5 .

Here are the results:

3.1. Results and Observations for $m = 3$

We started by varying the mutation probability from 0.01% to 1.00%. We observed that the number of generations follows rapidly from more than 10^6 for $p = 0.01\%$ to around 10^4 for $p = 0.10\%$ before falling almost linearly after that. From $p = 0.01\%$ to $p = 0.20\%$, the values of the number of generations we get are as follows.

p	Number of Generations
0.01	1831063.898
0.02	429729.042
0.03	226439.646
0.04	116149.032
0.05	77583.598
0.06	48549.63
0.07	43776.896
0.08	32071.126
0.09	25697.61
0.1	18935.59
0.11	18184.562
0.12	15057.056
0.13	14448.802
0.14	12537.386
0.15	11894.524
0.16	10647.674
0.17	8837.212

0.18	8028.724
0.19	8356.936
0.2	6859.836

In this interval, the number of generations decreases almost exponentially. The number of generations is of the order of 10^6 for $p = 0.01$, order of 10^5 as p ranges from 0.02 to 0.04, of the order of 10^4 for p ranging from 0.05 to 0.16, and then in the four digits. Not only the number of generations, but also the rate of decrease in n also decreases sharply.

After $p = 0.2$, the decrease in number of generations stabilizes to a more linear trend, however the rate of decrease tends to decrease as we move towards higher probabilities of mutation.

As the probability ranged from 1% to 100%, the number of generations remained almost constant.

Figure 1: The line graph showcases the variation in the number of generations as the probability of mutation ranges from 0.2% to 1% for $m = 3$. The curve depicting the decrease is still convex as the magnitude of slope is decreasing, yet the rate of decrease is much lower compared to the scenario when p ranged from 0.01 to 0.2. After $p = 0.5$, the decrease is almost linear.

Figure 2: This graph depicts the variation in the number of generations as the probability of mutation ranges from 1% to 100% for $m = 3$. Interestingly, while there's a sharp decrease in the number of generations needed as p ranges from 0.01% to 1%, in this interval there is no clear trend in the data. The number of generations oscillates between 720 and 980 with the maxima and minima both being achieved around $p = 60\%$. The fact that there is no significant variation here is surprising as mutations are the 'driving force' of the process of de-extinction, and it's unclear why the trend would be significantly different to that for p less than 1.

3.2. Results and Observations for $m = 4$ and 5

For $m = 4$ and 5 , we only conducted simulations as the probability of mutation ranged from 1% to 100% because simulating trials where p was less than 1% wasn't computationally feasible.

Figure 3: The graph depicts the variation in the number of generations as probability of mutation ranges from 1% to 100% for $m = 4$. The pattern is similar to that for $m = 3$ with there being no clear trend.

Figure 4: This histogram shows the distribution of values of n for $p \in (1\%, 2\%, \dots, 100\%)$ for $m = 4$. This somewhat resembles a Gaussian distribution, with values in the middle being

more common than those on the extremes.

Figure 5: The graph depicts the variation in the number of generations as the probability of mutation ranges from 1% to 100% for $m = 5$. Once again, the pattern is similar to that for $m = 3$ and $m = 4$ with there being no clear trend.

Figure 6: This histogram shows the distribution of values of n for $p \in (1\%, 2\%, \dots, 100\%)$ for

$m = 5$. Similar to the case for $m = 4$, this somewhat resembles a Gaussian distribution, with values in the middle being more common than those on the extremes. However, the distribution is significantly more right-skewed in this case than for $m = 4$, for which it is slightly left-skewed.

4. Discussion

For $n = 3$, we see a significant fall in the value of n as p ranges from 0.01% to 1%, following which it's mostly constant.

We observed that there is no significant trend in the number of generations as p ranged from 1% to 100% in for any value of m . However, the statistical distribution of the values of n as p ranges from 1% to 100% is interesting and is close to a Gaussian distribution for $m = 4$ and $m = 5$. Yet, it's slightly left skewed for $m = 4$, and significantly right-skewed for $m = 5$, for which we have found no clear justification.

5. Conclusion

In this project, we have studied de-extinction using a computational approach to back-breeding dynamics. Studying a toy model of breeding in organisms, we have used Python simulations to estimate the number of generations it would take for the genotype of an extinct ancestor to reappear in the gene pool.

As expected, we observed a significant drop in n as p ranges from 0.01% to 1% before the value stabilizes. However, as p ranges from 1% to 100%, the value of n shows no clear trend. This is surprising because mutations are the driving force behind the de-extinction process, and the independence of n on p in this interval was unexpected. Looking at the statistical distribution of n for p ranging from 1 to 100%, we observed a distribution that was almost Gaussian, but was slightly right-skewed for $m = 4$ and significantly right-skewed for $m = 5$.

5.1. Limitations of the Study

This study uses a simplified model of back-breeding with only two organisms per generation and a simplified model of genetic recombination. As a result, our model does not fully capture the genetic diversity in larger populations. Additionally, the model assumes a constant mutation rate, even though in nature, the mutation probability varies over time due

to environmental and genetic factors.

The model also doesn't take into account factors such as natural selection, genetic drift, and recombination, all of which have an impact on genetic outcomes. Additionally, due to computational constraints, the back breeding process has only been studied for certain values of number of chromosomes and probability of mutation. Using values of parameters closer to that for the specific organism for which de-extinction is being studied could provide deeper insights but will require greater computational power.

5.1. Future Recommendations

Future work could enhance accuracy by incorporating larger populations, varying the probability of mutation, and taking into account finer genetic mechanisms. By taking more parameters into account, the accuracy of the model can be increased to make it more representative of the actual back breeding process. Additionally, more in-depth studies could be carried out to simulate the de-extinction process for specific organisms, allowing for deeper and more relevant insights.

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